

Effect of Shoes on Lower Extremity Pain and Low Back during Prolonged Standing on a Sloping Medium

Ghassani Shabrina, Billy Muhamad Iqbal, Danu Hadi Syaifullah

Abstract: Media with 16° slope is an effective solution to reduce low back pain risk caused by prolonged standing. In this study, we examine the effect of shoes on lower back pain caused by prolonged standing for 2 hours on sloping medium. However, prolonged standing has another major risk: lower extremity pain. Many studies have shown that this risk can be affected by shoes type or characteristic. Hence, lower extremity pain risk is the main concern in this research. Two types of shoes observed in this study are Safety Shoes and Slip-On Shoes, as these are the most widely used in the manufacturing industry. Using the Surface Electromyography (S-EMG) method, the difference in Medial Gastrocnemius muscle response was measured against both types of shoes. The study showed that both types of shoes have different muscle activation values and the Safety Shoes showed greater activation. This result proves that, type of shoes may affect the amount of lower extremity pain caused while standing for 2 hours on sloping medium and Safety Shoes poses a greater lower extremity risk. Both Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and Foot Pain Questionnaire methods supported the finding. While the results of VAS method found standing for 2 hours on sloping medium has a greater lower extremity pain than low back pain risk. Foot Pain Questionnaire method indicated that the activity of standing for 2 hours over sloping medium causes a high pain on thumb toe and the back of foot. Based on this study, it can be concluded that it is necessary to design a special shoe for prolonged standing occupation on a sloping medium that can reduce the lower extremity pain risk, besides low back pain risk.

Keywords: Biomechanics, ergonomics, lower extremity pain, low back pain, prolonged standing, shoes, surface-electromyography.

I. INTRODUCTION

Standing for a long period (more than 30 minutes out of 1 hour) has a high risk of low back pain [1]. Prolonged Standing Strain Index classifies the risk based on the standing duration, standing continuously for more than 1 hour with 4 hours accumulation a day has an unsafe rating criterion with a high-risk level [2]. Coenen, et al. (2017) who has reviewed 26 journal articles conclude that the major risks of prolonged standing occupation are low back pain and lower extremity pain [3]. Unfortunately, prolonged standing can't be removed because many occupations, particularly in manufacturing industries, still need prolonged standing to maintain their productivity. Low back pain risk also cannot be ignored, National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke found that 80% adults have been diagnosed for low back pain and this

risk had cost 34.600 dollars per 100 employees per year including direct medical costs and indirect costs due to decreased productivity [4].

Numerous studies have been done to solve this problem such as anti-fatigue mat, shoes with soles, foot rests and vibrating tools, but those studies found all of the solutions were not significant in reducing the risk of low back pain [5]–[7]. One of the solutions that may reduce the risk of low back pain effectively is a medium with 16° slope which is able to reduce the risk by 59.4%. The research was observed by performing a prolonged standing activity for approximately 2 hours, on the sloping medium [8]. However, there is another major risk of prolonged standing activity, which is lower extremity pain, or pain from the pelvis to the toes [3]. With an altitude of 8.6 cm (barefoot) or more (with footwear) the posture of the body, especially the lower extremity, is similar as wearing 3 cm or more heels,

Corresponding Author: Billy Muhamad Iqbal. Industrial Engineering Department, Universitas Indonesia. Kampus UI Depok, Depok 16424, Indonesia. Telp. +62 21 788888. Fax +62 21 78885656. Email: billy.iqbal@ie.ui.ac.id

where previous research found that wearing high heels for a long time will force muscles to overwork and exhaustion [9]. While in a manufacturing industry activity, workers are not allowed without wearing footwear due to safety reasons, therefore the use of sloping medium with shoes will make the height change to higher in accordance with the height of shoe soles [10]. In addition to high sole, the shape of the sole also affects the amount of lower extremity pain users. Such a research conducted by Karimi et al. (2016) where shoes with stable soles have different muscle activity than those with unstable soles [11]. This first hypothesis in this study is, different shoes shall give different results on the amount of user's low back pain and lower extremity pain when using sloping media.

Reviewing the posture of the foot with the force of gravity and the user's body mass, the sloping media creates a posture that will provide a force down, which can push the toe to press the front side of the shoe, causing the toe to feel pain due to the shoe coat. Moreover, this tool is certainly designed to be used for long period standing. Additionally, while Safety shoes have a hard material toecap. Slip-On shoes have a narrow shape vamp. The second hypothesis in this study is the usage of both type of shoes on sloping media will make the user uncomfortable on the front foot.

Therefore, the main purpose of this study is to evaluate the effect of the Safety shoes and Slip-On shoes on lower extremity pain and low back pain during prolonged standing on a sloping medium.

II. METHODS

Seventeen volunteers, 9 male and 8 female (average age 20 ± 0.767 years, female mass 55 ± 6.179 kg, male mass 67.855 ± 5.22 kg, female height 160.62 ± 3.88 cm, male height 171.44 ± 4.17 cm, female shoes size 38-39, male shoes size 42-44) from Universitas Indonesia student population were participated. Participants were limited for those who never experienced low back pain and chronic low extremity pain (never hospitalized and never been unable to perform any activity for more than 3 days), never performed surgery on the low back to the toes, normal foot shape, did not do work relating to prolonged standing during the last 12 months, included in the category of healthy foot after filling the Manchester Oxford Foot Questionnaire (average MOxFQ score $88,281 \pm 4,737$).

In this study, two types of shoes, commonly used in

the manufacturing industry were observed. First, King's KWS 800 Safety shoes with hard and heavy characteristic. Second, Slip-On PX 179 with soft and lightweight characteristic. Both types of shoes are depicted in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Shoes Observed: Safety Shoes (Left) and Slip-On Shoes (Right)

A. Data Collection

This research used objective and subjective methods, the objective method used was the measurement of Medial Gastrocnemius muscle activity with Myotrac Infiniti Surface-Electromyography which is intended to measure how much pain occurred in the lower extremities. Surface Electromyography (S-EMG) in this research used a bipolar mode with two electrodes of 8 mm placed on the medial gastrocnemius muscle with an intercellular distance of 1.5 to 2 cm and one electrode placed in a neutral position. The measured skin portion was cleaned with alcohol and abrasive pad to remove the non-conductor and lubricated paste conductor to strengthen the flow of electricity. Mean Absolute Value data was taken in every 15 minutes out of 2 hours of data retrieval time while standing. The Maximal Voluntary Contraction data was taken 2 hours before data retrieval on one foot in standing position and rests on the front of the foot to normalize the muscle activity data.

The subjective method used was 100 mm Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and Foot Pain Questionnaire. VAS was used to categorize the pain felt by the responses in lower extremities and lower back separately for data taken in every 15 minutes out of 2 hours of data retrieval time. VAS values are categorized based on the level of pain felt by respondents with 11 levels of pain. Category 1 (No Pain) was the lowest pain value with score 0 and Category 12 (Unable to Move) was the highest pain value with score 100, the details of the categorization is described in Table 1. Foot Pain Questionnaire was used to map the pain felt by the respondents at 10 points on the lower legs and 9 points

on the foot the respondents filled out the questionnaire after 2 hours of data retrieval. The data was collected for 2 hours with the position of the respondent standing upright on a sloping medium with an adjustable table set 5 cm below each elbow, the task was typing in purpose to replace the usual work occupied with prolonged standing. Range between the first and the second of data retrievals (each type of shoes) for each respondent allowing no less than 2 days for the recovery of respondents' strengths.

TABLE I. VISUAL ANALOG SCALE CATEGORIZATION

Category	Name	Score
1	No Pain	0
2	Ignored	1 - 9
3	Minimal	10 - 19
4	Mild	20 - 29
5	Un-comfortable	30 - 39
6	Moderate	40 - 49
7	Distracting	50 - 59
8	Distressing	60 - 69
9	Unmanageable	70 - 79
10	Intense	80 - 89
11	Severe	90 - 99
12	Unable to Move	100

B. Data Processing

In this study, S-EMG was done using the following formula

$$\%MVC = \frac{MAV}{MVC} 100\%$$

Where MVC is Maximal Voluntary Contraction and MAV is Mean Absolute Value. Both of them was measured with Mikro Volt Unit.

C. Statistical Analysis

SPSS (IBM Statistical 25) was used for all statistical analyses. First, descriptive statistics were done for all of the variables. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) Repeated Measures Test was performed to analyze the effect of footwear conditions, standing time, and gender on medial gastrocnemius muscles activity and subjective pain responses, separately. Post Hoc Least Significance Difference was also performed to analyze the effect of each standing time.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Electromyography

From Surface-Electromyography method, it is found that Shoes Types and Time factor indicate that there is enough evidence to reject Ho so that Shoes Types and

Time factor proved to have an effect on Medial Gastrocnemius muscle activity either right or left side based on S-EMG result. The results are given in Table 2. This is clarified by the average graph of the MVC% of the Medial Gastrocnemius muscle in Figure 2, showing the difference between the two types of shoes, where Safety shoes had higher muscle activity during minute 15 to minute 120 for the left side and from minute 15 to minute 90 for the right side, which indicated that the muscle activity when wearing Safety shoes is bigger than the Slip-On shoes either on the right or left side. The same goes for time factor where the muscle activity tended to increase from minute 0 to minute 120. There was a slight decrease after reaching the peak in minute 75 and rising up again until minute 120.

The ANOVA Repeated Measure Test results are in line with previous research by Karimi et al. in 2016. Comparing the activity of the medial gastrocnemius muscle and tibialis anterior between the shoes with stable soles and those with unstable soles, the shoe factor showed a significant difference in the medial gastrocnemius muscle activity. In this study the type of shoes factor in the gastrocnemius medial muscle activity showed the same result. However, there are differences in the time factor in which Karimi's research (2016) has no significance. For interaction between factors, the results of this study and Karimi's (2016) research yielded corresponding results [11]. It can be concluded that in this study findings, Safety shoes compared with Slip-On shoes increase the medial gastrocnemius muscle activity which was also supported by Coenen et al. (2017) research that the medial gastrocnemius muscle is one of the two muscles that will indeed increase its activity in prolonged standing activity followed by anterior tibialis muscle.

TABLE II. STATISTICAL RESULTS FOR S-EMG

Source	Medial Gastrocnemius - Right		Medial Gastrocnemius - Left	
	F	Sig.	F	Sig.
Gender	0,497	0,504	2,728	0,143
Shoes	5,577	0,05	8,208	0,024
Time	19,08	0	18,907	0
Gender * Shoes	2,199	0,182	0,881	0,379
Gender * Time	0,862	0,475	1,111	0,369
Shoes * Time	5,336	0,004	0,753	0,513
Gender * Shoes * Time	0,718	0,675	0,4	0,747

Differences in medial gastrocnemius muscle activity in both types of shoes are possible because the muscles hold heavier load when wearing Safety shoes where it has more weight compared to Slip-On Shoes.

While standing, the medial gastrocnemius indeed increases its activity to keep the body upright.

Fig. 2. S-EMG Average Graph (%MVC vs Minutes)

B. Visual Analog Scale

TABLE III. STATISTICAL RESULTS FOR VAS

Source	Lower Extremity Pain - Right		Lower Extremity Pain - Left		Low Back Pain	
	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.
Gender	4,966	0,061	7,455	0,029	0,096	0,766
Shoes	12,788	0,009	13,408	0,008	27,565	0,001
Time	130,578	0,000	113,041	0,000	68,101	0,000
Gender * Shoes	5,743	0,048	11,911	0,011	6,955	0,034
Gender * Time	0,601	0,562	1,181	0,340	0,916	0,395
Shoes * Time	1,948	0,163	1,859	0,173	11,626	0,000
Gender * Shoes * Time	1,791	0,197	1,174	0,335	4,872	0,023

Fig. 3. VAS Average Graph (%MVC vs Time)

Visual Analog Scale method on lower extremity pain result showed that Shoes and Time factor affect lower extremity pain to both right and left based on VAS results. This is clarified by the average graph of the VAS value in Figure 3. It is clear that the difference between the two types of shoes; Safety shoes has a higher VAS value at any time from the minute 15 to the minute 120 indicating that according to the respondents when wearing Safety shoes, the lower extremity of the respondents was more painful than the Slip-On shoes on both the right and left sides. Moreover, the result of time factor is the VAS value is constantly increasing from minute 0 to minute 120 on both the right and left side.

The ANOVA Repeated Measure Test results are in line with previous research conducted by Karimi et al. (2016) and Lin et al. (2012) which compared the pain in lower extremities on different shoes. In both studies, the shoe factor and time had a significance of 0.00 to the value of VAS so it can be concluded that the shoe and time affect the amount of pain felt by the respondent. However, different results were shown in the interaction between shoes and time, in this study both factors have a significance of more than 0.05 but in research conducted by Karimi et al. (2016) these two factors have a significance of 0.00 different from those of Lin et al. (2012) which showed similar results with this

[11],[12].

Visual Analog Scale method on low back pain shows the results of ANOVA Repeated Measure Test showed that type of shoes and time factor affect the low back pain based on the VAS results. This is clarified by the average graph of the VAS value in Figure 3, a clearly visible difference between the two types of shoes, Slip-On shoes have a higher VAS value at any time from the minute 15 to minute 120 indicating that according to the respondents when wearing Slip-On shoes, the bottom of the respondents feels more pain than the Safety shoes.

Based on the limited knowledge of researchers, they have not found any research on the effect of shoes on low back pain quantities during prolonged standing activity yet. However, the results of the ANOVA Repeated Measure Test are in line with research conducted by Armand et al. in 2014 that the difference in shoes can affect the amount of low back pain according to the VAS results. Although in previous studies the activity was running instead of prolonged standing. Slip-On shoes have a greater low back pain risk than Safety shoes which can be caused by the features of KWS 800 Kings Safety shoes's shock absorption insole that is used to reduce back pain when prolonged standing.

VAS value data of each respondent for each type of shoe was categorized based on the pain level. For the slip-on shoes, most respondents felt the highest pain in Category 6 (Moderate) for right lower extremity pain and Category 5 (Uncomfortable) for the other side. For safety shoes the VAS value is in the higher category of Category 8 (Distressing) for right lower extremity pain and Category 7 (Distracting) for the other side. This result indicated that when a person is wearing Slip-On shoes while performing activities for 2 hours standing on sloping media, most people felt the pain constantly but still able to perform the activity. But for Safety shoes, most people tend to always feel pain and cannot do the work which interferes with the individual productivity. In a manufacturing industry, this will diversely affect the daily operations of the company.

In addition, the highest value observed on Slip-On shoes is in the Category 9 (Unmanageable) while for Safety shoes is at Category 10 (Intense). This indicated that there is a possibility of pain experienced by a person while performing 2 hours standing activity on sloping media, where the individual can only think about pain and cannot perform other activities. Surely this will be very detrimental to the individual itself and to where the individual is working. Therefore, Karimi et al. (2016) and Lin et al. (2012) in their study also stated

that shoe is one of the appropriate ergonomic interventions in the work environment in order to reduce the discomfort and pain felt by workers [11], [12]. Thus, the results of VAS values in this study indicate that Slip-On shoes are definitely better Safety shoes are not recommended as footwear to do work that involved prolonged standing for 2 hours on sloping medium.

When the result of VAS values on lower extremity pain is compared with the result of VAS values on low back pain, both had distinct differences. As already mentioned before, for lower extremity pain most respondents are in the range of Category 8 (Distressing) and Category 5 (Uncomfortable) whereas for low back pain most respondents are in the Category 3 (Minimal) which interpret that the pain is only mildly felt by the respondent. This shows that the pain experienced by respondents at lower extremity is much higher compared to that experienced at low back. This also shows that the use of media tilt indeed lowers low back pain users but not on lower extremity pain users.

C. Foot Pain Questionnaire

The results of Foot Pain Questionnaire method are shown on the heat map. For the lower legs of both the right and left sides, in the point 5 (Lateral Calcaneal Nerve) and point 6 (Extensor Digitorum Longus Tendons) shows a bright red color for safety shoes. This indicates that these points are the most painful points felt by the respondents on the legs down at category 4 but for Slip-On shoes the point is at a lower category. This indicates that wearing Safety shoes causes higher pain at point 5 (Lateral Calcaneal Nerve) and point 6 (Extensor Digitorum Longus Tendon) as compared to Slip-On shoes.

Both shoes showed the average pain on the front side of lower leg that classified at category 3. For the back side of lower leg, the pain is in the lower category 2. At the top for point 1 (Gastrocnemius Muscle), the muscle studied at EMG research is included in category 3 whereas point 10 (Tibialis Anterior) is a muscle that also contracts high when standing prolonged is at the lowest category 1.

Gastrocnemius Muscle and Tibialis Anterior is a muscle that increases its activity due to prolonged standing (Coenen et al., 2017). However, it is found in this study that it is not the point which considered as the most painful by the respondents, but the points around the soles of the feet were observed to be the most painful. Shoes soles of both left and right sides of the heatmap are illustrated in Fig. 5. In Safety shoes, almost all points are in categories 4 and 5 but the highest point

of pain (located in category 5) is point e (Lateral Calcaneal Nerve) and d (Medial Calcaneal Nerve). Slip-On shoes gained better results compared to Safety shoes where most points are in category 3 but there is a point with the same value with Safety shoes; points a (thumb) which belongs to category 4 in both shoes. However, on the left Slip-On shoes point d (Medial Calcaneal Nerve) is also included in category 4. This indicates that the Slip-On shoes have lower pain value than Safety shoes even though at point d the difference is not significant.

In contrast to Caravaggi et al. research in 2016, which stated that when standing, the entire point on the sole of the foot has the same pressure [10]. But this study shows a different result, then it indicates that the sloping medium gives the effect of different pain due to different pressure at certain points on the sole of the foot of points a, c, and d. High categories at points c and d can be caused because the point becomes the fulcrum of the body on the feet where when standing on a flat floor the entire load will be spread over the sole of the foot but when using the sloping media the load rests on the sole of the hind leg (point c and d) resulting pain on that point high.

TABLE IV. FOOT PAIN QUESTIONNAIRE LEGENDS

Category	Color	Scale
5	Dark Red	55 – 65
4	Red	45 – 55
3	Yellow	35 – 45
2	Light Yellow	25 – 35
1	Green	<25

Fig. 1. Foot Pain Questionnaire Heat Map for Lower Legs – (a) Right Leg Slip On Shoes (b) Right Leg Safety Shoes (c) Left Leg Slip On Shoes (d) Left Leg Safety Shoes

Foot Pain Questionnaire Heat Map for Foot – (e) Right Foot Slip On Shoes (f) Right Foot Safety Shoes (g) Left Foot Slip On Shoes (h) Left Foot Safety Shoes

According to Newton's Law I on the incline which states that when objects are stationary then when an object is on a sloping medium, there will be a gravity of the object multiplied by the inclination of the oblique media slope that made it slide down but retained by the friction force. In this case, the researcher assumed that the weight of the body multiplied by the inclination of the tilted media slope is the force that causes the foot to shift forward, so that the thumb presses the toe cap. Hence point a (thumb) is in a high pain category. The frictional force that keeps the body in place, is the friction between the soles of the feet and the soles in the shoes. An increasingly rugged shoe sole will have a greater frictional force. This frictional force occurs in the rear legs (points c and d) where the point is the highest hit point on the sole of the foot as it is the fulcrum of the body. Thus, Safety shoes that have soles in the rougher ones have a higher value compared to Slip-On shoes that have deeper insoles and subtler. Other points on the sole of the foot which have a high value in Safety shoes also became a friction force because the surface of the foot was in contact with the soles in the shoe, thus it yielded a greater value

compared to Slip-On shoes. But still, the gravity multiplied by the sine of the sloping media has the same value for both shoes so that this problem cannot be accommodated by both of shoes type.

IV. CONCLUSION

This research can be concluded based on the observation of low back pain and lower extremity pain of the respondents by using Visual Analog Scale, Electromyography, and Foot Pain Questionnaire method. It is found subjectively that shoes affect the muscle activity of Medial Gastrocnemius, and also affect lower extremity pain and low back pain on the use of media tilt for prolonged standing. The category of pain for Safety shoes included severe pain that can interfere with user productivity. From the results of VAS, it was also found that lower extremity pain risk is greater than the risk of low back pain. Foot Pain Questionnaire results found that sloping medium caused a high pain in the thumb and both could not accommodate it.

From these results, it is recommended for future research of shoe design to provide additional foam arch in the central shoe insole so that the working downward force can be restrained so that the toes do not touch the vamp. The vamp needs to be based on soft material so that when the toes touch it, it will not strain the toes. The insole can be made with a smoother material to reduce the friction force so that the sole of the foot does not feel pain and heat. In addition, the weight of the shoes should also be considered so that the burden experienced by the foot is not too high and does not increase muscle activity of Gastrocnemius Medial. This study has a limitation of the pain which is at the foot points being measured subjectively by respondents, which is important for the shoe design. For further research, pressure in the soles of shoes can be measured first to get more valid results. It is also possible to propose a special shoe redesign for prolonged standing activity on the tilt media to reduce user's risk of lower extremity pain. Manufacturing industries that want to use sloping media for their work stations should pay attention to the shoes effect. Safety shoes are generally not recommended to be used on a sloping medium and this study recommends to instead, use slip-on shoes.

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